

The MATRIX Ontology - Semantic Memory for Multi-Agent Experience Transfer, Reasoning and Interaction eXchange

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Abstract. Multi-agent collaboration has a long established record in reinforcement learning, and has gained momentum in the recent years with the breakthroughs in language-based intelligence. At the same time, there has been demonstrated a significant potential of joining LLM and RL agents in a single pipeline. Memory is the central component of multi-agent pipelines, both in learning and inference: it stores long-term experience, agents' transactions in the working memory, other learning artifacts. However, given a plethora of protocols, environments, and experience representations, the challenge is to implement interpretable decision-making between RL agents (neural layer), and LLM agents (symbolic) in working memory, and experience transfer in the long run. Driven by the idea that agents should be able to collaborate autonomously, and learn how to use, transfer, and synthesize new knowledge and processes, we propose a graph-based memory model, which can be shared and reused by both RL and LLM agentic teams on any representation level. This memory model is a collection of RDF graphs, allowing for neural and symbolic representations at the same time, and providing interoperability and explainability of knowledge graphs. In the current paper, we introduce the MATRIX ontology (Multi-Agent Experience Transfer, Reasoning and Interaction eXchange), a conceptualization behind the shared memory layer, that can serve as a memory, decision, and experience model for heterogeneous agentic teams, and show its applications in different use cases.

Keywords: ontology for multi-agent experience transfer · semantic memory for multi-agent teams · multi-agent reinforcement learning · knowledge graphs for shared memory representation · experience transfer between neuro-symbolic agents.

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1 Introduction

AI agents — whether LLM-based or trained via reinforcement learning (RL) — are widely used to incrementally improve on setting the task, proposing solutions, planning the execution, and making insights. Currently, in the generative AI community, the understanding of an "agent" becomes continuously diffused via building agents of arbitrary granularity and functionality and often disregarding the presence of an environment with its feedback. In contrast, notions of "agent" and "multi-agent" have a well-established theoretical foundations in RL, especially its MARL (multi-agent) part[1]. Recent research shows the benefits of joint multi-agent setups [6] that combine LLM agents (operating on symbolic and sub-symbolic level) and RL agents (operating in vector spaces). Moreover, both produce valuable artifacts of the learning process, which can be interchangeably reused. Despite these advances, a major bottleneck remains: LLMs work on symbolic and sub-symbolic level, and RL agents operate almost exclusively in vector space. In complex open environments, agents often expected to reason under uncertainty, justify and explain their decisions to others, and reuse knowledge from past interactions. These tasks require shared, interpretable memory of learned artifacts that allows for reasoning and knowledge transfer and reuse.

To address this, we propose a shared semantic memory model structured as a knowledge graph, governed by the MATRIX Ontology (Multi-Agent Experience Transfer, Reasoning, and Interaction eXchange, see Sec.4). This memory framework stores artifacts generated by humans, LLMs, and RL agents and supports explanation, experience reuse, and facilitate agents' ability to share knowledge, adapt, and collaborate during decision-making.

Our **contributions** are therefore summarized as follows:

- A shared memory model for multi-agent teams to store and exchange tasks, decisions, and learning processes (see Sec.3, 4);
- MATRIX Ontology as a unified schema for neuro-symbolic agents' experience representation and reasoning (see Sec.4);
- Mechanisms for policy reuse, experience sampling, and artifact sharing to accelerate learning (see Sec.5.1);
- A symbolic representation that enables both semantic reasoning and integration with neural models for adaptive behavior (see Sec.4.1).

This shared memory approach directly addresses the challenges of cross-agent knowledge sharing and coordinated decision-making, providing a foundation for explainable and adaptive collaboration in mixed teams of AI and human agents.

2 Related work

The development of agentic memory and multi-agent interaction models has recently gained significant attention[1]. Burtsev et al. [9] propose a hierarchical memory framework that allows LLM-based agents to accumulate and structure experiences for more autonomous behavior. Complementing this, RDF-based

memory for LLM agents [8] introduces graph-based knowledge storage, enabling agents to organize and retrieve relational information effectively. In the area of agent communication and collaboration, Sumers et al. [10] review cognitive architectures for language agents, discussing how agents handle reasoning, memory, and interaction. However, their work does not offer a formal ontological framework to support heterogeneous agent collaboration. The taxonomy of multi-agent collaboration by Microsoft [6] directly addresses the problem of experience transfer between diverse teams, highlighting key challenges such as role specialization and agent heterogeneity. Further, recent advances in LLM-driven multi-agent systems (Salakhutdinov et al. [12], [7]) explore how agents can reason, plan, and act jointly, often relying on large language models.

3 Methodological Approach for Ontology Development

The MATRIX ontology has been developed using the LOT methodology, which offers industry-oriented best practices for ontology development, publication, and maintenance [5]. It defines iterations over a basic workflow, which comprises four major steps (1) Ontology requirements specification; (2) Ontology implementation; (3) Ontology publication; and (4) Ontology maintenance.

Ontology requirements specification included the use case specification, the purpose and scope of the ontology and the requirements proposal (Sec.3.1). Defining the purpose, scope and requirements took several iterations including a conceptual modeling step leveraging the BFO ontology (see Sec.3.2), and fast prototyping for the refining of competency questions. Moreover, requirements were derived from the results obtained by the authors in the previous experiments on knowledge graphs injection in RL agent’s learning process[11].

Ontology implementation started with conceptualization of the learning process in multi-agent teams with a focus on aligning LLM and RL teams whenever possible, that instances of both teams could reuse experience of other agents stored in the semantic memory, backed by the MATRIX ontology. Classes, relations and attributes are described in Sec.4.

Publication of the ontology has been accomplished following the guidelines implemented in the metaphactory platform, with a review process. **Maintenance of the ontology** will be done via the metaphactory platform on the metaphacts GmbH Ontology Repository*.

The primary objectives of this model include:

- **Standardized representation** of learning artifacts at an abstract level for multi-agent decision-making.
- **Facilitation of semantic queries**, allowing efficient retrieval and reuse of past experiences.
- **Learning process and experience sharing**: The ontology enables multi-agent teams to document, retrieve, and share learning experiences effectively.

* <https://ontologies.metaphacts.com/matrix/>

By structuring past interactions, decision pathways, and environment observations, it allows agents to benefit from prior experiences rather than learning from scratch in each new scenario.

- **Improving decision-making in multi-agent and mixed LLM-RL teams:** By structuring knowledge representation in a graph-based format, the ontology allows for enhanced decision-making by providing contextualized past experiences, best practices, and failure scenarios. This is particularly useful in mixed teams where LLMs and RL agents must collaborate, as it offers a structured approach to decision-making alignment.
- **Experience retrieval and transfer learning:** The ontology supports efficient retrieval of relevant past experiences based on contextual similarity, agent type, or environmental factors. This enables agents to quickly access useful prior experiences, facilitating adaptive learning and reducing the exploration-exploitation dilemma.

3.1 Ontology Requirements: Learning Process and Experience Exchange in Multi-Agent RL and LLM Teams

When designing the MATRIX ontology, we assumed it to serve as a memory and experience model for different types of agentic teams. This has posed several questions to clarify:

- *What are the learning strategies in MARL, and how do agents share experience and communicate?*
- *What artifacts do the agents learn in LLM and MARL teams?*
- *Which learning and interaction artifacts should be stored in the memory to allow further experience transfer and memory operations (compression, inference, forgetting, etc.)?*
- *What are decision-making strategies in multi-agent teams?*
- *What roles do the agents have in multi-agent teams and what are the known principles for agents' teaming?*

The analysis of existing approaches in multi-agent reinforcement learning, and of the structure in LLM-based agentic workflows has resulted in the careful selection of concepts (both occurants and endurants), that were settled as the core of the multi-agent memory. Depending on the actual team setup (LLM, RL, or mixed) this core can be augmented with more specific classes and properties, which would be at the same time reusable by the team of a different structure. To define the scope and requirements of our ontology, we formulate the following **competency questions**:

1. **Task and agent classification:** What types of tasks require an environment, and which agent types are suitable for them?
2. **Environment configuration:** How are different environments structured, and what setup parameters define them?
3. **Performance metrics:** Which environmental conditions yield the best and worst performance, and under what circumstances?

4. **Task-specific team performance:** How do performance metrics vary across tasks, learning strategies, and team configurations? (See Sec.5.2)
5. **Action-to-reward mapping:** Given a set of observations, what actions did agents take, and what were their resulting rewards?
6. **Experience reuse:** How can new teams leverage prior experiences to optimize learning and execution strategies? (See Sec.5.1)
7. **Decision-making process tracking:** How do agents record, analyze, and refine their decision-making pathways?
8. **Inter-agent communication:** How do agents share observations and knowledge, and how does this impact team performance?

3.2 BFO Ontology as Conceptual Modeling Framework

Our ontology design is based on well-established ontological perspectives on processes and objects. Specifically, we adopt the distinctions outlined by Heller and Herre [3], who differentiate between endurants (continuants) and processes based on their relationship to time:

- **Endurants** are individuals without temporal parts or phases, existing within a fixed time frame. They can be indexed by temporal boundaries.
- Processes, classified as **occurrents**, have temporal parts and cannot exist at a singular time boundary. A typical process consists of a sequence of planned steps; however, in dynamic environments, the feasibility of each step depends on external conditions and observations.

Transitions between states shape the knowledge graph in the agent’s memory, mapping historical data to current states and potential future actions. A similar modeling approach has been applied in work on the Basic Formal Ontology [2]. To resolve conflicts between representing processes as pre-planned sequences and their dependence on dynamic environmental conditions, we draw on Zemach’s [13] dichotomy between **continuant** and **occurrent** ontologies, a distinction also implemented in **BFO 2** [4].

4 The MATRIX Ontology

The MATRIX Ontology provides a structured way to represent and organize learning processes, decisions, observations, and policies, enabling agents to share, reuse, and adapt experiences across tasks and domains. The ontology integrates both symbolic and sub-symbolic artifacts, making it suitable for mixed teams and diverse architectures. The ontology is represented in Fig.1. The MATRIX Ontology is grounded in foundational distinctions between processes and objects, following the formal separation of occurrents (processes and endurants (entities)) as defined in BFO. This dual view allows MATRIX to model time-dependent learning and interaction processes alongside static configurations and roles of agents.

Processes are temporal entities composed of evolving, interdependent steps. These classes are designed to represent both learning and decision processes, essential for reconstructing and analyzing agent experiences:

- **Episode**: A bounded sequence of agent-environment interactions with outcomes (rewards, observations).
- **Trial**: A specific learning or inference run, defined by unique parameters and configurations.
- **LearningProcess**: A complete learning or fine-tuning trajectory, often spanning multiple episodes or trials.
- **Checkpoint**: A saved state of an agent or team that can be restored for continued learning or analysis.
- **Task**: A goal-oriented activity that agents seek to solve; includes environmental context and constraints.
- **DecisionStep**: A discrete step in which an agent or team makes a decision based on available external resources and internal models.
- **LearningStep**: A part of learning pipeline, such as policy update for RL agents or prompt update for LLM agents, enabling experience acquisition and adaptation.

Endurants are time-independent entities that exist as individuals during and across processes. These classes encode agents' roles, capabilities, and the context for action:

- **Action**: A specific operation an agent can perform within an environment; may include parameters and interpretations (e.g., LLM prompts, control commands).
- **Policy**: A strategy or mapping from observations to actions, represented as symbolic rules, neural networks, or LLM-based plans.
- **AgentRole**: The role or specialization of an agent within a team (e.g., teammate or learner), supporting heterogeneous cooperation.
- **Team**: A group of agents that collaborate on a task, characterized by structure and division of roles.
- **Agent**: An individual entity capable of autonomous behavior; described by type (RL, LLM, Human), capabilities, and roles.
- **ActionSpace**: The set of all possible actions available to an agent in a given environment.
- **EnvironmentResponse**: Feedback from the environment, including observations and rewards, that guides agent adaptation.
- **AgentInput**: The information or planned actions provided by the team members and available within a decision step before taking a next decided action, which may include observations, inter-agent communications, and resources (e.g., external tools, human input).

Several modeling principles shaped the design of MATRIX Ontology to meet the unique demands of multi-agent learning and reasoning:

1. **Explicit Representation of Decision and Learning Steps:** The inclusion of `DecisionStep` and `LearningStep` classes allows detailed capture of how decisions are made, what knowledge is used, and how learning occurs, making it possible to analyze, explain, and optimize agent behaviors.
2. **Role-based Agent Modeling:** Through `AgentRole` and `Team`, MATRIX supports flexible team configurations, where agents with different capabilities (RL agents, LLMs, humans) collaborate. This role-based design encourages specialization and coordination, essential for scalable multi-agent systems.
3. **Focus on Experience Transfer and Reuse:** By capturing rich contextual information around actions, decisions, and outcomes, MATRIX facilitates retrieval of past experiences and supports transfer learning. New agents or teams can sample relevant past cases, analyze decision pathways, and adapt previous knowledge to new tasks.
4. **Support for Inter-Agent Communication and Interaction:** MATRIX models `AgentInput` and `EnvironmentResponse` to capture not only environmental dynamics but also inter-agent communications, essential for collaborative decision-making in mixed teams.

4.1 Decision Model

One of the most complex and variable aspects of ontological modeling in MATRIX is the representation of decision-making model within a team of agents. The architecture and specificity of these processes can vary widely: from trivial models, where an action proposed by an agent is directly accepted as a decision without any modification, to complex iterative models that require applying sophisticated theories and computational models such as game theory, neural networks, Kalman filters, graph-based reasoning or LLM-based agents. Additionally, decision-making may involve external resources and tools, including human assistance, making the process even more elaborate.

Figure 2 illustrates a generalized scheme of a multi-agent decision-making model (left) and provides a detailed view of how heterogeneous inputs from diverse agents can be represented as a set of vectors (right).

In the development of MATRIX Ontology, we intentionally avoided creating numerous specific classes to represent every possible variation of decision-making models, as this would lead to a large and overly complicated set of classes, significantly increasing the complexity of agents’ semantic memory structure. Instead, we opt for a single abstract class that serves as a generic representation of any decision-making model, regardless of its internal mechanics, and a class `Decision step` that represents iterations made by agents during their communications. The specific characteristics and mechanisms of each model are captured through a set of object and data properties, including:

- `communication` (exchange of information among agents),
- `constraints` (limitations or rules affecting the decision),
- `interpretator` (mechanism for interpreting agent inputs),
- `processor` (component for processing inputs or options),

- resource (external tools or human inputs used during decision-making),
- hasDecidedAction (final selected action),
- hasPredictedAction (anticipated or forecasted action).

Fig. 2. Decision Model Structure and its Artifacts in the MATRIX Ontology Model. *The example shows agents' input sharing in the vector space.*

5 Ontology Validation & Usage

We validate the ontology for two types of teams (a team consisting of only RL agents, and a team of only LLM agents) with particular use cases focusing on the reusability of semantic memory artifacts and experience transfer. An important aspect of the validation was to showcase applicability of the ontology model for capturing multi-agent learning scenarios, which were previously challenging to bring together.

5.1 MATRIX Ontology as Semantic Memory for Reinforcement Learning Teams: Policy Transfer Use Case

In multi-agent reinforcement learning (MARL), "agents learn optimal decision policies by trying actions and receiving rewards, with the goal of choosing actions to maximize the sum of received rewards over time. While in single-agent RL the focus is on learning an optimal policy for a single agent, in MARL the focus is on learning optimal policies for multiple agents and the unique challenges that arise in this learning process"[1]. One of the research lines in improving RL

efficiency is policy transfer, when another team of agents starts learning from already achieved results. Given a plethora of neural architectures and optimizing algorithms, choosing and applying an appropriate policy becomes challenging. To demonstrate the usability of the MATRIX ontology to improve MARL learning, we have implemented experiments with MARLLib* in Multi Particle Environments (MPE). MPE are a set of communication oriented environment where particle agents can (sometimes) move, communicate, see each other, push each other around, and interact with fixed landmarks*.

Fig. 3. SPARQL Query and Diagram Fragment illustrating MATRIX Ontology Validation for Policy Transfer between MARL Teams. Natural language request: *Find checkpoints of policies optimized with multi-agent PPO algorithm learned by a team of RL agents in the MPE (multi-particle) environment*

We have populated memorable objects with the team setup, learning process and artifacts for the **simple spread** scenario, and were able to validate most of the competency questions and decision model on it. In **simple spread**, an **RLTeam** consists of 3 **Agents** in a discrete **Action Space**, and **Learning Process** is organized in **Episodes** and **Learning Steps**. Each **Learning Step** consolidates **Agent Input**, caused **Environment Response**, and **Decision Step**. At the end of an **Episode** a **Checkpoint** with intermediate **Policy** parameters is produced. Based on the modeled **MemorableObjects**, it is possible to retrieve **Checkpoints** trained with particular **Algorithm** parameters and under given **Environment** configuration. Fig.3 shows a relevant ontology fragment (1), a SPARQL query (2) to retrieve policy checkpoints learned in a particular environment and optimized with a particular algorithm (3).

* <https://marllib.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>

* <https://pettingzoo.farama.org/environments/mpe/>

5.2 MATRIX Ontology as Semantic Memory for LLM Teams: Multi-Agent SPARQL Query Generation

To validate the ontology for the LLM teams, we have modeled SPARQL query generation task in a multi-agent setup, and populated memorable objects for two teams. One of the teams was built of SPARQLTranslation (LLM) and Reflection (LLM) agents, and another team joined SPARQLTranslation (LLM), Retriever (LLM+Tool) and ProbabilisticInference (RL) agents. In both teams, SPARQLTranslation agent was the Learner, and other agent helped him as Teammates. The team works in an Environment, consisting of a knowledge graph, F1-score as a reward function, and retrieved results as observations. An Action of the infinite Action Space is the SPARQL query, generated by the team and executed by the SPARQLTranslation agent. Decision Step was defined as a conversation between team members, trying to improve their prompts with obtained Observations and Rewards. Each attempt to generate or improve the query was considered as a Learning Step, and learning artifacts were logged in a Dataset for further LLM fine-tuning at the end of each episode.

Fig. 4. SPARQL Query and Diagram Fragment illustrating MATRIX Ontology Validation for Experience Transfer across Multi-Agent LLM Teams. Natural language request: *What was the structure of multi-agent teams working on SPARQL query generation task which learning resulted in high rewards?*

Agents accumulate learning artifacts, retrieve positive and negative samples for LLM fine-tuning and summarize the input. The image 4 shows a relevant ontology fragment (1), a SPARQL query (2) to learn about the structure of the teams, which got the highest rewards (3).

6 Future Work

Multiple studies of multi-agent interaction and learning show the central role of experience transfer for agents' decision-making, and some existing approaches

already represent working memory as a graph. With introducing the MATRIX ontology, we provide heterogeneous agentic teams an instrument operating both on neural and symbolic levels. Thus, agents can get inspiration from the decision making process across other teams and develop a common language. In future, we aspire to proof the value of the MATRIX ontology as a cognition layer, focusing on the questions *How can agents extract, generalize, and adapt knowledge from past experiences to novel situations?* and *How do agents decide when to explore novel strategies versus relying on proven approaches?* (exploration vs. exploitation balance), and improve neuro-symbolic multi-agent learning.

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